

“Survey of Lichens of Nagaon, Assam”

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Abstract:

The symbiotic association of algae and fungi, named as Lichen play an important role in Ecosystem. They are used traditionally as medicine since the time of the first Chinese and Egyptian civilizations. Their utilization as medicine has been cited in different pharmacopoeias of the world. The biological screening of lichen for active molecules can be grouped in to three main categories, antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-cancer. Urbanization is a major threat to Lichen diversity. Here we make a survey of lichens from different sites of Nagaon and prepare a list on the basis of their habitat. Lichens were identified by critically surveyed the literatures and government recognized lichen laboratory. The aim of this study is to enrich the current status of lichen habitat.

Key words: Symbiotic, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-cancer, Urbanization.